

Searching for substellar companion candidates with *Gaia*

I. Introducing the GaiaPMEX tool

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ABSTRACT

Context. The *Gaia* mission is expected to yield the detection of several thousands of exoplanets, perhaps at least doubling the number of known exoplanets. Yet only 72 exoplanet candidates have been reported with the publication of the *Gaia* third data release or *Gaia* DR3 (GDR3). Although the harvest is expected to occur with the publication of the astrometric time series in the DR4 at the eve of 2026, the GDR3 is already a precious database to search for exoplanet beyond 1 au.

Aims. With this objective, we characterized multiple systems by exploiting two astrometric signatures derived from the GDR3 astrometric solution of bright sources with $G < 16$. We have the proper motion anomaly, or PMA, for sources also observed with HIPPARCOS, and the excess of residuals present in the renormalised unit weight error (ruwe) and the astrometric excess noise (AEN). Those astrometric signatures give an accurate measurement of the astrometric motion of a source seen with *Gaia*, even in the presence of non-negligible calibration and measurement noises.

Methods. We introduce a tool called *Gaia* DR3 proper motion anomaly and astrometric noise excess, or GaiaPMEX for short, that is able, for a given source, to model the astrometric signatures that are hidden within the PMA, ruwe and AEN, by a photocenter orbit due to a companion with certain mass and relative semi major axis to the primary star (sma). Comparing to their actual measurements from GDR3 and HIPPARCOS, GaiaPMEX calculates a confidence map of the possible companion's mass and sma. This tool allowed us to determine for any source of interest, using data derived from the GDR3 astrometry, and HIPPARCOS when available, if it may be a binary (or planetary) system and what could be all possible companion's mass and sma.

Results. We found that the astrometric signatures can allow identifying stellar binaries and hint to companions with a mass in the planetary domain. The constraints on mass are, as expected, degenerate, but when allowed, coupling the use of PMA and ruwe or AEN may significantly narrow the space of solutions.

Conclusions. Thanks to combining *Gaia* and HIPPARCOS, planets are expected to be most frequently found within 1–10 au from their star, at the scale of Earth-to-Saturn orbits. In this range of sma, exoplanets with mass down to $0.1 M_J$ are more favorably detected around M-dwarfs closer than 10 pc to the Earth. Some fraction, if not all, of companions identified with GaiaPMEX may be characterized in the future using the astrometric time series that will be published in the forthcoming DR4.

Key words. exoplanets detection ; astrometry ; radial velocities

Note from Authors

Appendices E to H are printed in the following pages.

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Appendix E: Cumulative density functions of the calibration noise estimation through the GDR3 database with respect to magnitude and color

Fig. E.1. Cumulative density functions (blue lines) of the σ_{calib} distribution of GDR3 data at diverse bins through the magnitude-color domain. Only the σ_{calib} close to the mode are shown. The dotted black and red lines show respectively the 41st-percentile and median of the whole distribution. The cyan line is the result of the iterative localisation of the mode. The horizontal green lines shows the location of the median of the plotted domain.

Appendix F: Detailed RUWE, AEN and PMa maps for the illustrative examples shown in Section 8

Fig. F.1. HD81040 GaiaPMEX maps from AEN (red), RUWE (purple) and PMa (blue) constraints. See Section 8 for specific details and the combined ruwe+PMa map. The known companion in this system is shown as a yellow circle.

Fig. F.2. Same as Fig. F.1 for AFLep.

Fig. F.3. Same as Fig. F.1 for HD 23596.

Appendix G: Individual detection rates map with α_{UEVA} or PMA for GJ 832

Fig. G.1. Theoretical detection rates with respect to M_* and parallax around GJ 832, through using UEVA only. Details of the maps are similar to Fig. 27.

Fig. G.2. Same as Fig. G.1 using PMa only.

Fig. G.3. Theoretical detection rates with respect to mass and sma around GJ 832. Left: detection through UEVA only; right: through PMa only.

Appendix H: Error and noise tables

Table H.1. Extract of the table of noises with respect to RA and DEC, here at DEC=-49° (column omitted) including that of GJ 832 (RA≈21°), determined in both 5p and 6p datasets.

RA (°)	$\sigma_{\text{att},5\text{p}}$ (mas)	$\sigma_{\text{att},6\text{p}}$ (mas)
5	0.078	0.075
6	0.078	0.075
7	0.078	0.076
8	0.078	0.076
9	0.078	0.076
10	0.078	0.076
11	0.079	0.076
12	0.079	0.076
13	0.079	0.075
14	0.079	0.075
15	0.079	0.075
16	0.079	0.075
17	0.078	0.075
18	0.078	0.075
19	0.078	0.075
20	0.078	0.075
21	0.078	0.075
22	0.078	0.075
23	0.078	0.076
24	0.079	0.076
25	0.079	0.076
26	0.079	0.077
27	0.080	0.077
28	0.080	0.078
29	0.079	0.078
30	0.079	0.078
...
...
...
330	0.079	0.079
331	0.079	0.079
332	0.079	0.078
333	0.079	0.078
334	0.079	0.078
335	0.079	0.078
336	0.079	0.078
337	0.079	0.078
338	0.079	0.078
339	0.079	0.078
340	0.079	0.078
341	0.079	0.079
342	0.079	0.079
343	0.079	0.079
344	0.079	0.080
345	0.079	0.080
346	0.077	0.079
347	0.077	0.078
348	0.077	0.078
349	0.077	0.077
350	0.077	0.077
351	0.076	0.076
352	0.077	0.077
353	0.078	0.078
354	0.078	0.079
355	0.079	0.080

Table H.2. Extract of the table of noises with respect to magnitude and color, here at $Bp - Rp = 2.2$ (column omitted) including that of GJ 832 ($G \approx 7.7$), determined in both 5p and 6p datasets.

G	$\sigma_{\text{AL},5\text{p}}$ (mas)	$\sigma_{\text{calib},5\text{p}}$ (mas)	$\sigma_{\text{AL},6\text{p}}$ (mas)	$\sigma_{\text{calib},6\text{p}}$ (mas)
3.20	—	—	0.020	1.560
3.30	—	—	0.031	1.581
3.40	—	—	0.030	1.598
3.50	—	—	0.033	1.470
3.60	—	—	0.030	1.372
3.70	—	—	0.024	1.315
3.80	—	—	0.013	1.206
3.90	0.024	—	0.013	1.174
4.00	0.020	—	0.020	1.121
4.10	0.016	0.871	0.024	1.077
4.20	0.023	0.864	0.026	1.042
4.30	0.027	0.855	0.026	1.006
4.40	0.025	0.846	0.024	0.970
4.50	0.021	0.819	0.021	0.936
4.60	0.024	0.775	0.019	0.917
4.70	0.029	0.707	0.019	0.902
4.80	0.036	0.639	0.018	0.887
4.90	0.035	0.582	0.015	0.876
5.00	0.033	0.531	0.003	0.873
5.10	0.034	0.498	0.024	0.818
5.20	0.033	0.465	0.040	0.717
5.30	0.032	0.410	0.047	0.619
5.40	0.034	0.363	0.044	0.567
5.50	0.039	0.302	0.040	0.506
5.60	0.040	0.262	0.041	0.414
5.70	0.040	0.231	0.039	0.389
5.80	0.040	0.202	0.037	0.361
5.90	0.039	0.189	0.035	0.331
6.00	0.037	0.174	0.033	0.310
...
...
...
7.70	0.093	0.149	0.095	0.203
...
...
14.00	0.113	0.073	0.132	0.264
14.10	0.119	0.073	0.137	0.260
14.20	0.125	0.073	0.143	0.260
14.30	0.132	0.073	0.150	0.263
14.40	0.138	0.074	0.156	0.264
14.50	0.145	0.073	0.164	0.265
14.60	0.152	0.073	0.170	0.265
14.70	0.160	0.074	0.178	0.264
14.80	0.168	0.074	0.186	0.264
14.90	0.176	0.075	0.194	0.264
15.00	0.184	0.076	0.202	0.266
15.10	0.194	0.077	0.211	0.266
15.20	0.204	0.078	0.221	0.267
15.30	0.214	0.079	0.230	0.269
15.40	0.225	0.080	0.241	0.271
15.50	0.236	0.081	0.251	0.274
15.60	0.248	0.082	0.263	0.275
15.70	0.261	0.083	0.274	0.278
15.80	0.274	0.084	0.287	0.278
15.90	0.288	0.084	0.298	0.274